

Dental Health of Youth in the World at the Current Stage

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Abstract: This article discusses the dental health of young people in the world today and the fight against oral diseases. It provides information based on examples and analyzes on how to keep teeth healthy in today's youth, the causes of disease, measures to prevent disease, and how young people should follow a healthy lifestyle to prevent oral cavity diseases.

Keywords: morphofunctional pathologies, nutrition, adaptation, physical development, medical ethics, social-hygienic.

The health status of the younger generation in any state is the main component of public well-being. There is a generally accepted definition of youth: "... this is a special social group of the population, united by certain age boundaries, intensive mental work in the process of vocational training, specific learning conditions, lifestyle and mentality at the age of 16 to 25 years" [1].

Young people are characterized by rapid adaptation to new trends in society, increased intellectual and emotional stress due to huge amounts of new necessary information; the vast majority of young people do not have a sleep and nutrition schedule, or proper rest [2,4]. Therefore, young people are recognized as "a special group in biological and social terms with a high risk of persistent health and developmental disorders" [3].

In the new millennium, significant deterioration in the general health of the country's youth has been observed, a significant increase in the prevalence of morphofunctional pathologies, a decline in average physical development, an increase in chronic diseases and health problems have been stated [4,5,11]. Researchers are most concerned about junior students at universities, which is due to heavy workload from studies and systematic violations of diet and rest [6,7]. Up to 27% of first-year university students already have significant health problems [8,11], which gives reason to think that the problem of poor health of students started during the school period and only gets worse at university due to increased social, psychological and academic stress [5,8,12].

Protsenko A.S. [9] believes that by the end of school, almost 80% of schoolchildren already have pathologies of physical development and health, which causes difficulties and obstacles in obtaining the desired profession.

Shevlyakova M.A. states that about 90% of those entering universities have at least one chronic disease [10,13].

Kabayan O.S. and Kulikova V.A. unanimous in their thoughts: "...a sharp change in the ideological attitudes and values of society, the emergence of market relations in medicine did not have a very favorable effect on its condition" [12,14,17]. Taking into account the extremely important social role of young people, it is necessary to develop effective methods for preserving and restoring their health [15,18].

The health problems of the younger generation around the world are of great importance. Back in 1985, the UN declared the “International Year of Youth” [20,22]. In 2000 The European Union focused on the health of young people in 2009. youth health is recognized as a priority for the CIS countries [16,21].

To improve the health of young people, Western countries and Europe have concentrated their efforts on the social and hygienic aspects of young people’s lives: “environmental factors, lifestyle and prevention of bad habits, popularization of sports and a healthy lifestyle” [24,28].

The most important factors determining the level of quality of life of university students are considered: “... adaptation to the conditions and mode of study, new natural and climatic factors, changes in the quality of food in connection with leaving home, socio-psychological tension, various behavioral characteristics of boys and girls, social -hygienic, ethnic and cultural factors, level of medical activity, hygienic awareness and attitudes towards a healthy lifestyle” [22,23]. For some young people and girls, these factors, taken together, cause exacerbations of existing chronic pathologies and the development of new diseases [25,29]. Competent, timely, targeted and effective psychophysiological assistance in adapting to new conditions of the social environment is one of the main prerequisites for successful studies and mastering professional skills among young people [15,26].

The profile of the university has virtually no effect on the occurrence and development of morphofunctional disorders and chronic pathologies [25,27], however, certain nuances of training in medical universities affect medical students [17,19], thus: “...the fragmentation of educational facilities, significant time costs for moving, the need to comply with the rules of medical ethics and deontology, causing emotional stress in students, the impact of factors in the hospital environment that adversely affect the young body” [22,28] thirty.

Nutrition is of significant importance in the adaptation of students, the balance and regimen of which determines normal health, promotes high mental and physical performance, and contributes to quick and easy adaptation in the social environment [3,13,21].

The actual hygiene and diet of students states: “... in most cases, nutrition is irrational, often does not correspond to the energy value of the daily diet and the actual energy expenditure of the body, with insufficient intake of proteins, fats, a number of minerals and vitamins” [2,16,28].

Protsenko A.S. provides the following data: “...the nutrition of the majority of students aged 16-25 is irregular and unbalanced, 58% of them eat by snacking, 64% use fast food, 65% note a lack of proteins, vitamins, microelements and an excess of carbohydrates, carbohydrates in the student diet are mainly represented by pastries and sweets, 75% of students consume them daily and several times, 63% systematically eat sweets between meals, 53% always include sweet desserts in their diet, and 38% consume sweets at night” [7,9,14].

Smoking is not just a bad habit, but a global epidemic of tobacco smoking, with which there is an active war in most developed countries [6,8,12]. However, in parallel, there is an increase in tobacco smoking among young people and a decrease in the age at which regular smoking begins. The predominant number of chronic non-infectious diseases is caused by tobacco smoking, which causes and accelerates their progression [41, 20-21]. Among students, 27-44% of those surveyed have a persistent addiction and smoke constantly [29,30].

Alcohol is another significant risk factor for deteriorating people’s health: “...excessive consumption and abuse of alcoholic beverages is a risk factor for the development of a number of chronic non-communicable diseases”. Of the university students, 36-69% drink alcohol [25,28].

Low physical activity of the population and especially young people is recognized as a significant problem of public health in almost every country [19,27]. Protsenko A.S. writes: “...only 31% of medical students prefer active recreation, and in addition to physical education

classes provided for in the schedule, only 49.2% of boys and 24.6% of girls go in for sports” [30,31].

Research on the adaptation of first-year students to study at a university revealed: “... only 58.7% of students have satisfactory adaptation, and 12.5% have unsatisfactory and even failure of adaptation, which determines their psychological and physical health” [22,32].

Disturbances in biorhythm and quality of life among students occur due to the fact that lack of time to study and complete necessary tasks leads to a lack of night sleep, which is especially clearly seen among nonresident students. Protsenko A.S. cite the following in your research: “... about 60% of students live and study in a state of chronic lack of sleep and stress, 76.9% of first-year students have less than 7 hours of sleep at night, about a third of 3rd year students allow themselves only 4-5 hours on weekdays sleep every day, 50% of 4th year students sleep reaches 7-8 hours every day, and a general lack of time for sleep and rest is stated by 64.8% of students”.

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